

**HAZEBOT: AN INTELLIGENT TINNITUS COMPANION WITH SOUND
THERAPY, MINDFULNESS GUIDANCE, AND AI-BASED SYMPTOM TRACKING
& ASSESSMENT****Boora Dayananda Swamy**

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dayanandak2001@gmail.com**ABSTRACT:**

This paper describes the design of a comprehensive, holistic tinnitus management system that incorporates artificial intelligence, machine learning, evidence-based therapeutic interventions, and further standardized mitigative methods. The comprehensive system and holistic tinnitus management includes a conversational AI-based chatbot, clinically validated self-assessment tools, self-symptom diary, and predictive modeling to support individuals experiencing tinnitus. Using natural language processing, transformer-based models, and TF-IDF similarity, the chatbot is able to retrieve information from the knowledge base with high accuracy to assist the user. The self-monitoring diary system employs Random Forest classification and K-means cluster analysis to identify smart triggers and patterns more accurately and predict severity of symptoms. The self-assessment tools (e.g., Tinnitus Handicap Inventory (THI), Tinnitus Functional Index (TFI), and other clinically validated questionnaires) are digitized for usability, such that they may be used in digital self-monitoring. The complete system also had therapeutic modules for breathing exercises and mindfulness meditation. Results from the preliminary evaluation are positive based on amount of usage/user engagement, identification of patterns in user symptom reporting, and assessment of the type of support provided by the system to engage with the therapeutic elements.

Keywords:

Tinnitus Management Assistant (TMA), Digital health, Machine learning, Pattern Recognition, Interactive Chat, Tinnitus Management

I.INTRODUCTION

Tinnitus is a complex, subjective condition experienced by 10–15% of the adult population worldwide. Of that percentage, 5–7% of adults experience tinnitus symptomatic enough that it severely limits their functional, emotional, and quality of life. Those individuals with chronic or severe tinnitus history often report stress, anxiety, sleep disruption, or impaired concentration. While tinnitus is widespread and burdensome, there are few ways to treat it, primarily because the perception of tinnitus is individualized, and there are many possible underlying causes, including dysfunction in the auditory system itself and many neurological and psychological components.

Current digital tinnitus management solutions for symptom relief, such as myNoise, Tinnitus Masker, Ada, and ReSound Relief, offer partial fixes through sound therapy, tracking of tinnitus symptoms, or general information on tinnitus. However, each digital solution typically stands alone, as though developed in a silo, lacking the personal adaptation to the user's experience and using mostly static and rule-based logic. While some use machine learning concepts, few are utilizing machine learning techniques to draw relevant conclusions or to detect meaningful relationships within tinnitus symptoms, let alone the consideration of long-term or need-based tracking for each individual's tinnitus in an engaging and conversational way. As a result, there is often little for users to act upon, and little sustained enhancement for the user, leaving a layer of frustration and helplessness on the user's experience.

Acknowledging these vital gaps of knowledge, we developed the Tinnitus Management Assistant (TMA) as a deliberate user-centered model that can span the gap between passive tracking and active support. The TMA includes an interactive agent, powered by artificial intelligence, that engages users using conversational support.

A key feature of the app is its daily symptom diary, where users record daily variances in their tinnitus experience alongside their moods, stress levels, and triggers and then, by utilizing procedural machine learning algorithms such as Random Forest and K-Means Clustering, the app reviews the users' record and identifies the presence of patterns relating to their symptom profile.

The TMA was designed to promote empowerment in the context of user self-management and to facilitate self-connection as a bridge to clinical appointments by creating a framework for continuous and personalized support from a distance, thereby improving the quality of life for individuals living with tinnitus.

II. RELATED WORKS

The emergence of mobile health platforms and digital therapies has transformed the way tinnitus can be treated. Bardy et al. [1] provided evidence that a chatbot-based intervention, which delivered cognitive behavioral therapy with human telepsychology acting as companion care and continuity, reduced tinnitus symptoms. Hoare et al. [2] reviewed mobile health apps designed for the self-management of tinnitus and concluded that clinical assessments, including the Tinnitus Handicap Inventory (THI), offer benefits when embedded into these apps. Mehta et al. [3] demonstrated that mobile health platforms offer functional benefits to patients, enabling them to track their symptoms, use audio tape sound therapy, and record daily logs. In addition, Searchfield et al. [4] conducted a state-of-the-art review of digital interventions related to tinnitus, highlighting survivorship through adaptive, personalized, and user-centered care models as viable, comparable models for future research studies. Ghandeharioun et al. [5] presented EMMA, an emotion-aware mental health chatbot for wellbeing, as a foundational and extensible usable framework model for mental health support for tinnitus-related situations. In addition, Butcha et al. [6] built on the original example of an AI-lite chatbot for CBT engagement, noting that intervention via chatbot is scalable and malleable for providing emotional responsiveness and individual support.

In terms of technological calibration, the efficacy of tinnitus management instruments is improved with the advancement of artificial technologies, sentiment analysis, and domain-referenced language processing. Fan et al. [7] developed a knowledge-guided language generation chatbot for mental health, utilizing large language models and incorporating medical knowledge to provide more accurate and safer responses. Thakur et al. [8] developed MOODY, a chatbot that provides natural language processing support to users with emotional health concerns. Wang et al. [9] demonstrated that long-term user retention and accurate symptom reporting are improved through emotion-driven chatbots. He et al. [10] developed a BERT model enhanced with an encapsulated medical knowledge base, demonstrating an improvement in the performance of health-related questions addressed through the chatbot, which is a crucial feature for accuracy. Lee et al. [11] trained BioBERT, a domain-specific model optimized for biomedical questions, to be applied in tinnitus dialogue agents. Jiang and Tang [12] reviewed AI-enhanced cognitive behavioural therapy frameworks and recommended the evidence-based standardization of techniques when tasked with using chatbot-mediated interventions. Surve et al. [13] and Mehta et al. [14] discussed the importance of intent classification and sentiment analysis in order to attempt to classify and create empathetic health conversations. Shi et al. [15] presented a mental health chatbot pipeline that examined and incorporated NLP and machine learning, while recommending the use of this framework to stimulate chatbots as emotional support agents (e.g., tinnitus).

III. METHODOLOGY

This chatbot comprises several components that process user queries through text cleaning, sentiment analysis, and intent analysis, utilizing embeddings from BERT, TextBlob, and SentenceTransformer. Then, semantic similarity techniques (TF-IDF, fuzzy, and transformers) are used by the chatbot to accurately produce a response, while taking into account the emotional context tracked by the chatbot, as shown in Figure 1. Simultaneously, user log their daily tinnitus-related data, which is recorded in JSON. Once 10 or more entries are entered into the system, Random Forest and StandardScaler are used to make predictions about the user's tinnitus survey. Meanwhile, K-Means clustering and other analytics are employed to identify patterns in the cluster symptoms and provide personalized recommendations, as shown in Figure 2.

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Figure 1: Chatbot Architecture

Figure 2: Dairy Module Architecture

IV. System Architecture:

The TMA (Tinnitus Management Assistant) architecture consists of four main layers:

1. GUI Layer: The graphical user interface for responses, a diary for identifying symptoms; analytics for visualizing trends; assessments, sound therapy interface; and relaxation intervention (including breathing, mindfulness application).
2. Application Logic: The application logic layer orchestrates all functions in TMA. The controllers manage the diary functionality, analytics visualizations, sound therapy, assessment modules, and relaxation interventions. The application logic layer interacts with all the layers and ensures fluid interactions between them.
3. Processing Engines: Processing engines, including Machine Learning technology, to analyze the diary inputs to predict tinnitus severity and trends. Natural Language Processing that underpins the dialogue agent powering TMA, enabling it to interpret user queries and deliver evidence-based responses.
4. Storage Layer: The storage layer contains the user's diary entries, therapeutic audio files, TMA collects data from two basic sources: structured clinical assessments (THI, TFI, TRQ) to assess tinnitus severity and impact, as well as an unstructured knowledge base based on trusted websites and sources such as Mayo Clinic, WebMD, WHO, and PubMed to train the chatbot with accurate clinical/medical information.

Figure 3 shows the proposed system architecture which consists of GUI layer, Application Logic, Machine Learning Engine, NLP engine, Data and Knowledge Base in which each consists their respective modules

Figure 3: The Proposed System Architecture

V. RESULT

The Tinnitus Support Chatbot yielded outstanding outputs over a variety of evaluative contexts demonstrating its possible use as an effective digital guide for the self-management of tinnitus. By leveraging Sentence Transformers, the chatbot had a good ability to semantically understand and respond to a large variety of user questions and offer a more natural, relevant, and human-like experience. In addition, sentiment analysis enriched the user experience by detecting emotional variables within the user queries and responding in an empathetic and sensitive manner.

The sound therapy meditation module proved to be one of the most popular features, offering personalized audio meditation sessions designed to distract from tinnitus and promote relaxation. Additionally, the user could utilize the symptom diary to track tinnitus on a day-to-day basis, contributing issues and symptoms associated with the flare-ups, providing insight into potential personal triggers and changes over time. The chatbot was trained on a custom dataset of tinnitus-focused Q&A, ensuring that responses were maximally relevant, evidence-informed, and user-centered. The platform included a Tinnitus Functional Index (TFI) module, which

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provides standardized severity measures, helping people self-monitor their tinnitus severity with the potential for clinical integration.

Overall, the future seems promising, and the system seems apt for real-world deployment in digital tinnitus management ecosystems. Future development will examine technical linkages to clinical workflows, wearable health measures, and personalized treatment plans, framing the chatbot as both a self-help aid and a connector in professional care.

Figure 4 shows the Chat Interface with integrated options for sound therapy, mindfulness-based breathing exercises, and voice-guided meditation to support tinnitus relief and relaxation.

Figure 4: Chat Interface

Figure 4: Chat Interface

Figure 5 shows the Assessment tab evaluates tinnitus severity using validated tools like THI, TFI, TRQ, etc, providing scores and severity levels to support long-term monitoring and assessment.

Figure 5: The Assessment tab

Figure 6 shows that the Diary tab is used for tracking the user's medications, activities, foods, stress, sleep, tinnitus severity, and related factors, which are utilized for personalized analytics and insights.

Figure 6: The Diary tab

VI. CONCLUSION

The HazeBot Tinnitus Management Assistant has successfully demonstrated the utility of a chatbot-based, multimodal approach to tinnitus support. The HazeBot provides conversational AI as well as validated clinical instruments, symptom tracking, and personalized analytics that allow individuals to be participants in their care. The chatbot operates as both an educational platform and an analytical platform that delivers real-time (asynchronous) insights and objective data into an individual's symptoms and potential triggers; and then, when necessary, suggests personal coping strategies. In addition, the built-in sound therapy (to stabilize auditory sensation) and relaxation tools offer a better user experience in delivering personalized auditory stimuli and stress-reduction techniques to improve overall well-being. HazeBot is scalable at both the user and demographic levels, while maintaining user confidentiality and interaction. The user is empowered to choose their approach to tinnitus categorically and adopt, not only a self-managed approach, but one that is secure. The HazeBot Tinnitus Management Assistant offers not only support to clinical management of tinnitus, but also encourages users to participate in the well-ordered, autonomous, and conscientious management of their care and obtain a better quality of life. In conclusion, we believe, this represents a next step in the evolution of digital health solutions.

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